

The construction of political authenticity: Jeremy Corbyn’s use of commitment-boosting *I think*

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Abstract

The last decade has been marked by the rise of a new breed of “authentic” politicians. Relative outsiders to the political institution, these politicians presented themselves as constituting a break from the (overly and overtly) mediatized and staged performance of politics by constructing authentic identities through various verbal and non-verbal resources. Starting from the social-constructionist view of identity as performance, this paper explores the performance of political authenticity by Jeremy Corbyn, ex-leader of the British Labour Party, in three political interviews held prior to the 2019 general elections in the U.K. In particular, the paper operationalizes the notion of indexicality, as used in recent, “third-wave” sociolinguistic research on identities and styles, to explore how Corbyn uses the epistemic phrase *I think* to construct his politically authentic identity. Through a close reading of Corbyn’s discourse in the three interviews, it seems that he uses *I think*, in its commitment-boosting variety, to construct his identity as an authentic politician — one whose values accord with his behavior and one who is deeply committed to the ideas and ideals that he espouses.

Keywords

Jeremy Corbyn, political authenticity, identity, social constructionism, sociolinguistics

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Introduction

The notion of an “authentic” politician, or an “authentic” candidate, might strike some as an oxymoron. Indeed, there appears to be a consensus in political science, communication, and media literature that trust in politicians, and the general political process, has been in a general state of decline in the past few decades in both Western and Eastern communities (McNair, 2004: 325; Rosanvallon and Goldhammer, 2008: 255-256; Bøggild, 2020: 2-3; Christophe et al., 2021: 4-7). The reasons presented in the wider literature are myriad: some argue that the general populace have developed an increased engagement with the liberal democratic state and the political process and, as such, expect better results (Norris, 2011: 10; Bertson, 2019: 215); others argue that there is a widespread belief that politicians are self-serving, working only for their own personal gain, that is constructed and exacerbated by the mass media (Bøggild et al., 2020: 270-271); others still argue that the “professionalization” of politics, both in terms of groups of “elites” taking hold over the state institutions and in terms of political communication itself, has helped create an increasing rift between politicians and the populace (Maarek, 2004: 213; Seymour, 2017: 198; Allen, 2019: 3); finally, most studies on waning political trust cast economic downturn as one of the main causes, if not the cause itself, of this decline (e.g., Armingeon and Guthmann, 2013: 424; Martinelli, 2016: 13; Bean, 2018: 18; Bertson, 2019: 213; Guriev and Papaioannou, 2022: 18; Bienstman, 2023: 15; cf. Dalton, 2017: 383).

Despite this general decline in political trust — perhaps even directly motivated by it — the “authentic” politician has become a central figure in politics recently. This is perhaps most highlighted by the rise of “outsider,” anti-establishment candidates whose popularity rests, in part, on their performance of “authenticity” and the media and the voter’s perception thereof. Indeed, the rise of politicians as Jeremy Corbyn and Nigel Farage in the U.K., Donald Trump and Bernie Sanders in the U.S., or even Jair Bolsonaro in Brazil (Peterson, 2005: 1094; Mueller et al., 2019: 3; Júnior and Gagliardi, 2021: 90) has led some to consider authenticity as an extremely important factor affecting the voter’s decision (Sorensen, 2018: 4; Luebke and Engelmann, 2022: 1-2), with some arguing that the 2016 U.S. presidential elections as well as the 2017 general election in the U.K. were mainly decided by who appeared most “authentic” to the voters (Hahl et al., 2017: 2-3; Enli and Rosenberg, 2018: 6; Shane, 2018: 1).

Researchers in fields such as sociology, communication, media studies, and (critical) discourse analysis have paid attention to this recent — or recently observed (cf. Seifert, 2012: 2; Greenberg, 2016: 485) — phenomenon. Such studies explore how candidates perceived as “authentic” performed their identities across different contexts and in different genres of political discourse. Indeed, researchers have explored, for example, the discourse of Jeremy Corbyn online and in his rallies (Bennister et al., 2017: 109; Kissas, 2019); the online discourse of “authentic” politicians in the Canadian Calgary municipal elections (Dumitrica, 2014); the online discourse of Donald Trump (Kreis, 2017; Shane, 2018) as well as his discourse in rallies (Montgomery, 2020; see also Montgomery, 2017); the online discourse of Hillary Clinton during the 2016 U.S. elections (Enli, 2017); and the online discourse of Scottish MPs and how they project authenticity (Margaretten and Gaber, 2012), among many others.

What unites these studies is their broad focus on authenticity as an identity or a style utilized and performed by the politician — one of ostensibly many that they deploy in various contexts. Starting from the notion that language and politics are inextricably intertwined (Chilton, 2004: 21, *passim*; Wodak, 2011: 217; Dunmire, 2012: 735), such studies have broadly adopted the

social-constructionist notion of authenticity as an identity performed by the politician (Coupland, 2001: 422, 437; Nyberg and Sveningsson, 2014: 440; Lacoste et al., 2014: 8-9; Sheinheit and Bogard, 2016: 3-4) in their explorations of what constitutes “authenticity” in the sphere of political discourse and communication, despite the disparate definitions and conceptualizations of what “authenticity” is and what being “authentic” entails.

While authenticity has been difficult to define in various disciplines and fields, the studies mentioned above and others have widened our understanding of how authenticity functions across a wide variety of political discourse genres. Yet, partly due to the difficulty of defining authenticity, and partly due to the mutability of identity and the markers that index it in recent sociolinguistic research (Silverstein, 2003; Eckert, 2008), current research on authenticity in political discourse has focused more on the content of a politician’s discourse rather than the actual signs or markers that constitute such a discursive identity, as argued by Shane (2018: 1). Indeed, most of the studies mentioned so far (e.g. Dumitrica, 2014; Kreis, 2017; Iszatt-White et al., 2018; Kissas, 2019; Mueller et al., 2019; Whittle, 2020; Lacatus and Meibauer, 2022) explore how politicians construct or perform their authenticity through a general overview of their discourses or those that the media constructs around them. As such, it seems that there is a gap in the literature whereby the construction of authenticity by politicians can be linked to distinct markers or features that are repeatedly deployed in specific contexts (Johnstone, 2009: 29; Sheinheit and Bogard, 2016: 4).

This paper, then, is an attempt to bridge this gap by drawing on the sociolinguistic conceptualization of style and identity (Rickford and Eckert, 2002: 6; Coupland, 2003: 428; Coupland, 2007a: 218-221) to explore how Jeremy Corbyn constructed his authenticity, which many argue is the reason for his meteoric rise as leader of the U.K. Labour Party (Diamond, 2016: 15–16; Richards, 2016: 12; Iszatt-White et al., 2018: 535–536; Allen, 2019: 1–2, 10), focusing particularly on his use of the epistemic phrase “I think” to project a politically authentic identity in three political interviews prior to the 2019 general election in the U.K.

1. Authenticity and the authentic politician

To say that authenticity is a nebulous concept would rather be an understatement. The concept has its roots in the Greek “*auto-hentes*,” and, generally, it refers to realness and truth to origin (Stiers et al., 2019: 4). However, the concept has been operationalized differently in various disciplines and fields. Indeed, something could be authentic because of its provenance or origin; because it’s a faithful representation of another entity or concept, or because it has been authenticated by a certain authority (van Leeuwen, 2001: 392–393; Peterson, 2005: 1087–1090). With regards to political discourse and communication, however, authenticity has been linked more to the notion of being true to oneself, or the congruence between one’s inner values and outer behavior (Cooper et al., 2005: 478; Umbach and Humphrey, 2017: 68; Iszatt-White et al., 2018: 537; Luebke, 2020: 637). Such a conceptualization starts from the idea that there is a clear, delimited inner self that people project when they are being authentic, and one’s authenticity is a matter of how well they are able to project this inner self. This strand of conceptualization has its roots in positive psychology research, with authenticity being considered a trait that can be assessed, quantified, and measured (Nyberg and Sveningsson, 2014: 439; Pillow et al., 2017: 2; Whittle, 2020: 443).

Taking authenticity as the congruence between a true, inner self and the outer behavior of a politician, however, has a few drawbacks, mainly the suggestion that there exists a monolithic

true self whose projection is the mark of authenticity. Nyberg and Sveningsson (2014: 440), for instance, criticize the psychology-based notion of authenticity, arguing that it is difficult for one to consistently know and express him or herself. This evaluation is shared by Mueller et al. (2019: 2), who argue that notion of authenticity as being true to oneself is problematic since it is impossible to gain an inside perspective on the “authentic” leader or politician’s inner ideas, thought processes, and values. The same argument is presented by Whittle (2020: 443) as well as Iszatt-White and Kempster in their article tracing and reviewing the concept of authentic leadership (2018: 360, 364).

Another, sounder and more nuanced conceptualization of authenticity, I believe, is the social constructionist view, whereby authenticity is viewed as an identity performed by the politician through various verbal and non-verbal cues or markers in different contexts (Luebke, 2020: 637). Through such a conceptualization, the focus is on authenticity as a persona or an identity that is interactionally, socially, and contextually constructed (Enli, 2015: 121–123; Shane, 2018: 2–3; Enli and Rosenberg, 2018: 3; Lacatus and Meibauer, 2022: 438). Through this performance of authenticity, politicians project their consistency in values, intimacy, spontaneity, and emotions to the voters and the media (Umbach and Humphrey, 2017: 7; Mueller et al., 2019: 2–3; Luebke and Engelmann, 2023: 3–4). This conceptualization incorporates the notion of being true to oneself, which is broadly the core of definitions of authenticity in its various guises (Gill, 2017: 41; Luebke, 2020: 637); however, there is still an inherent tension in the politician’s performance of authenticity and the nature of political discourse. Indeed, politicians have to strike a balance between appearing authentic to themselves and their values and appearing to have the same values, goals, and aims as their voters or constituents (Nyberg and Sveningsson, 2014: 447; Coleman and Firmstone, 2017: 260; Luebke, 2020: 637).

This conceptualization of authenticity as socially and relationally constructed can be related to recent sociolinguistic trends on the relationship between language, styles, and identities. As a field focused on the relationship between language and the social contexts in which it is used (Hernández-Campoy and Cutillas-Espinosa, 2012: 1), sociolinguistics paid a great deal of attention to language variation in different sociocultural contexts. This focus can be traced in terms of three “waves” of sociolinguistic research (Eckert, 2012; Coupland, 2007a: 219–220; Schilling, 2013). While a full discussion of the three stages of sociolinguistic research on intra-speaker language variation is outside the scope of this paper, the recent shift in the field to a broader, social-constructionist view of variation in language use and its relationship to identity and authenticity can be neatly operationalized to more concretely explore how authenticity is performed by Jeremy Corbyn.

Broadly, the third “stage” of sociolinguistic research on language variation views style and stylization as the speaker’s use of semiotic resources — both verbal and non-verbal — to construct and project their identities in different socio-cultural contexts (Coupland, 2001: 185–197). The third wave of language variation studies — dubbed generally the “Speaker Design” model (Schilling, 2013: 338; Hernández-Campoy, 2020: 146; cf. Coupland, 2007a: 80) — starts from the premise that style is the speaker’s creative, agentive use of various sociolinguistic resources to construct identities. Speakers are creative in their use of semiotic resources as they are not simply varying their use of language to converge into a set of pre-determined social positions or roles, but they are actively creating new identities and shifting into others as the contexts change (Coupland, 2007b: 221). Moreover, speakers are agents; their variation of language reflects an active choice on their part (Schilling, 2013: 338–339). More importantly

for the scope of this study, however, the speaker design model focuses on the linkage between language variation, language forms, and identities (Coupland, 2007b: 220; Eckert, 2012: 94).

Central to this linkage is the notion of indexicality and indexical order (Silverstein, 2003). Simply put, an index is a pointer to the context in which it occurred; it signals “some particular value of one or more contextual variables” (Silverstein, 1976: 29). In his discussion of meta-pragmatics and indexes, Silverstein provides some examples of such non-referential indexes such as sex indexes, which mark the speaker’s gender, and deference indexes, which mark respect, status, and rank, among others (1976: 30-31). Within the third-stage sociolinguistic research, such indexes as those referred to above have been understood to mark associations with certain groups, bracketed, as it were, according to geographical location or certain socio-economic criteria (Coupland, 2007a: 121; Schilling, 2013: 340). The focus of most of this third-stage research, however, has been on what is known as second-order indexes. That is, if a first-order index is a sign associated with certain groups, then a second-order index is that sign being associated with certain social traits, characteristics, and identities possibly associated with members of these groups (Eckert, 2012: 94; Schilling, 2013: 340). This focus on the link between linguistic variables and social meanings and categories through this notion of indexicality, then, is one of the primary features of such third-stage sociolinguistic studies (Eckert, 2012: 94).

Linguistic variables or features are seen as the core — the primitives — of how speakers construct their identities through the associations that obtain between such features and the social meanings that they index (Coupland, 2007b: 218). Identities are projected and constructed by the speakers — and can be negotiated, accepted, and rejected — in different contexts (Hernández-Campoy, 2020: 148). It is through this understanding of identity and social variation that we can explore the performance of political authenticity. By bringing together the social constructionist view of authenticity as an identity and the notion of style as the semiotic resources used by the speaker to construct their identities, we can trace a link between linguistic features used in various contexts and authenticity as an identity that politicians are attempting to construct through these features. Indeed, Bucholtz (2003: 408), for example, notes that there is an under-explored link between authenticity and identity in sociolinguistic research, arguing that the focus should not be on authenticity as an identity as “primordial,” but on authentication as the use of semiotic resources by speakers to present themselves as authentic. That is, the focus should not be on the identity, but on how users construct this identity using semiotic resources.

In summary, then, through a close analysis of how Jeremy Corbyn uses the semiotic resources available to him in different contexts, we can explore how he performs authenticity; that is, how he constructs this authentic politician identity. In particular, this study focuses on Corbyn’s use of the “epistemic phrase” (Kärkkäinen, 2003: 38) *I think* to establish himself as an authentic politician.

2. Data and context

The data for this study comprises a set of three political interviews with Jeremy Corbyn prior to the 2019 general election in the U.K., and the choice of politician, time, and political discourse genre are all highly motivated. First and foremost, Jeremy Corbyn is in many ways the quintessential “authentic” politician. Before the 2015 Labour leadership contest, Corbyn was largely only known as a rebellious backbencher who has been MP for Islington North since

1983 (Bennister et al., 2017: 104, 107). In fact, as Page notes (2019: 1321), Corbyn's entry into the leadership contest was simply a means to include the party's socialist, left-wing contingent in the contest. Virtually no one, not even Corbyn himself, expected that he would win the leadership contest (Ross and McTague, 2017: 96–97), and yet he did so with 59.5 percent of the total votes (Dorey and Denham, 2016: 25). Indeed, not only did Corbyn win the 2015 leadership election, but he also won the 2016 leadership challenge by an even larger margin, securing 61.8 percent of the total votes (Crines et al., 2017: 362), and he went on to lead the Labour party to gain 30 seats in the 2017 general election (Dorey, 2017: 319).

To many political scientists, researchers, and commentariat, Corbyn's success was primarily a function of his authenticity. Indeed, authors discussed how his relatively outsider status within the Labour party and the overall political establishment (Kissas, 2019: 6), his adherence to his values and ideals (Diamond, 2016: 6), his ostensibly "normal" discourse, as opposed to the usual "slick" and "smooth-talking" discourse of Westminster (Iszatt-White et al., 2018: 9), and even his sartorial style (Dean and Manguashca, 2017: 4) were all factors in him projecting this identity of an authentic politician. To a large extent, it is this authenticity that marked Corbyn and set him out against the modern image of a political class focused only on its own interests (Mueller et al., 2019: 1). This authentic image, then, can be explored in Corbyn's political discourse; that is, in his political speeches, interviews, and conversations, among others (Montgomery, 2001: 450), as it is political discourse that is the primary domain of the creation and establishment of political authenticity as an identity (Montgomery, 2001: 455; Bucholtz and Hall, 2005: 587).

Within Corbyn's political discourse, I chose to explore how he constructs this authentic identity in several interviews held before the 2019 general elections in the U.K., and the choice here is also highly motivated. As a genre of political discourse, interviews are taken to be more adversarial, more challenging and contested than, for instance, speeches (Montgomery, 2001: 450). Additionally, they seem to be less staged than speeches (Craig, 2010: 76). Of course, they can be partly staged, but within the political interview, the interviewer's primary role is to probe the politician and try to highlight the disconnect between what they think and believe and what they say, or between what they said before and what they say in the interview (Montgomery, 2001: 451–452; Montgomery, 2008: 261–262). Political interviews, then, seem to be a better context to probe how Corbyn construct his authenticity and maneuvers around the interviewer's moves, designed, as it were, to highlight this lack of authenticity.

Finally, the choice of time period is also highly motivated. The interviews all took place within less of a month of the 2019 general elections in the U.K., itself an unusual one given that the last general election happened only two years prior, in 2017. The 2019 general election has been termed by many to be the "Brexit" elections (Prosser, 2020: 5), and the "realignment" that occurred in the British political landscape before, during, and after the 2016 E.U. membership referendum (Cutts et al., 2020: 2) created a context in which Corbyn, I believe, had to rely on his authentic identity, which allowed him to win the 2015 Labour leadership contest and make considerable gains in the 2017 general elections, to navigate this realignment. At the time of the 2019 general elections, the British political landscape itself was highly divided across not only party lines — i.e., between the Conservative and the Labour parties — but also in terms of support for remaining in the E.U. and leaving the bloc (Fieldhouse et al., 2023: 3–4). Most importantly for the focus of this paper, Corbyn's authenticity, there were divisions in the Labour party itself on the way forward: accepting the results of the 2016 referendum and working towards a "softer" Brexit, or campaigning for a second vote on the issue (Goes, 2019: 86–87; Cutts et al., 2020: 5). Corbyn had to strike a balance between his democratic leadership of the

party and his own views and ideals, and this balance had to be sensitive to the fact that many in the Parliamentary Labour Party supported remaining in the E.U. and that many Labour voters supported leaving the bloc.

These many, oftentimes contradicting, contextual factors provide the tension in which Corbyn performs his authentic persona. Indeed, Corbyn, himself a lifelong Eurosceptic (Whittle, 2020: 452), had to project an identity marking him as true to his own values and ideals; as genuinely believing in Labour’s compromise towards Brexit, whether a softer exit agreement or a second referendum; and as an authentic leader whose mandate emanates directly from Labour supporters (Watts and Bale, 2018: 5–6).

3. *I think* and the performance of authenticity

Most studies on language variation and identity in sociolinguistics focus on phonological variables as indexing one identity or another by speakers. Starting from Labov’s (1963) seminal study of speakers in Martha’s Vineyard all the way to, for example, Coupland’s (2007b) study on the performance of identity by Labour politician Aneurin Bevan, the researchers focus on variation in phonological features, such as how some inhabitants of the Vineyard use a certain pronunciation of /ay/ to index their identity as members of Martha’s Vineyard in Labov’s study, or how Bevan switches between Received Pronunciation variants as well as Wales English variants — or a medium between the two — to index at times his identity as a member of the working class and at others his identity as a member of the political establishment in Coupland’s study (2007b: 223). Particularly within the third-stage of sociolinguistic research, however, there has been an expanded understanding of what constitutes styles; that is, what constitutes the resources speakers use to construct their identities. As such, style does not only include phonological variation, but also includes syntax, tone, politeness markers, discursive patterns, pragmatics, and, the focus of this study, epistemic stance markers (Coupland, 2007b: 218; Johnstone, 2009: 29-35; Schilling, 2013: 341).

Generally, epistemicity is taken to be the speaker’s commitment towards what they are saying; more specifically, the expression of different attitudes towards knowledge (Kärkkäinen, 2003: 19), and this epistemicity can be expressed in a variety of forms, including but not limited to phrases, tense, modal verbs, adverbs, intonation, or even prosody (Aijmer, 2015: 496). In terms of the semantics expressed by these items, it seems that their meanings, even those of modal verbs, are at least partially contextually determined; they seem to be “semantically inexplicit” (Kärkkäinen, 2003: 21). However, epistemicity is not only related to attitudes and commitments about the propositions expressed by the speakers, but it is also involved in construing and constructing the relationship between the speaker and the hearer/addressees. (Kärkkäinen, 2003: 25).

Of these epistemic devices or markers, the most interesting one used by Corbyn is *I think*, which is clearly visible in the three interviews explored in this paper. To determine how Corbyn constructs this authentic persona or identity through *I think*, however, we need to explore the various meanings that can be expressed by this epistemic phrase. The pragmatic function of *I think* in the literature is disputed, and the marker has been studied in various contexts and genres, such as spoken language in general contexts, (Kaltenböck 2010); spoken language, with a focus on interactions and conversations, (Kärkkäinen 2003); spoken language, focusing on press conferences (Fraser, 2010); spoken language in political interviews as well as

conversations (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000); spoken language in political discourse, mainly in political interviews (Fetzer 2008; 2014); and spoken language in political testimonies (Berlin, 2008) and political hearings (Berlin, 2011). The difference in the functions of *I think* could mainly stem from the notion that its function relates primarily to its context, as argued by Kärkkäinen (2003: 21) and Kaltenböck (2010: 258). Since this paper is mainly concerned with the use of *I think* in political interviews, it will focus on the discussion of the epistemic phrase by Simon-Vandenberg (2000) and Fetzer (2008; 2014).

Primarily, the functions of *I think* seem to be understood as either a device to mitigate epistemic commitment, as argued by Fraser (2010: 202), or as a device to both boost and mitigate epistemic commitment, as argued by, for instance, Simon-Vandenberg (2000), Kärkkäinen (2003), and Fetzer (2008; 2014). Here, commitment is taken broadly to mean that of the speaker towards the knowledge about, belief in, and truth of the proposition or proposal (Givón, 1993: 169; Kärkkäinen, 2003: 18; Fetzer, 2008: 385, 393-394). Despite their agreement on the general functions of *I think*, Simon-Vandenberg's (2000) and Fetzer's (2008; 2014) descriptions differ slightly in terms of the specific functions of the so-called pragmatic marker as well as the co-texts (or linguistic contexts) which motivate such functions. Indeed, for both authors, *I think* is understood as a commitment-boosting device when (epistemic phrase in bold; co-text affecting interpretation underlined):

- (i) The phrase is clause-initial and stressed, as in “**I think** it's ready by now” (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 47).
- (ii) The phrase occurs in the same clause as the conjunctions *and*, *but*, *because*; deictics including *now* and *then*; conjunctive adjuncts including *so* and *therefore*; and the modal verbs including *will*, *should*, and *must*, as in “And I think this conference has really shown that we're the Party that is open to new ideas” (Fetzer, 2008: 394).
- (iii) The “I think” clause contains intensifiers such as *really*; epistemic adverbs such as *certainly*; comment adjuncts such as *personally* and emphatic *do*, as in “**I certainly think** that it's quite wrong” (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 54).
- (iv) The phrase occurs near what Simon-Vandenberg (2000: 57) terms “evaluative lexis,” such as *marvellous* or *splendid* as in “**I think** Norman Fowler has done a marvellous job” (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 57).
- (v) The phrase occurs near an expression of necessity or obligation, as in “**I think** the important thing is for British business also to recognise the huge opportunities that do exist” (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 53).

Despite this general agreement between the two authors on the functions of *I think*, as synthesized above, they disagree somewhat on the extent of the co-text that affects the interpretation of the epistemic phrase as well as the elements affecting this interpretation. In Fetzer (2014), the author argues that the effective co-text of *I think* is limited to the clause in which it occurs; however, she also notes that certain elements found in clauses near the epistemic phrase could still affect its interpretation. For instance, the occurrence of an epistemic adverb signaling the speaker's low commitment, such as *probably* three or more clauses near *I think* could affect the interpretation of the phrase as commitment-attenuating rather than

commitment-boosting. In the following example, Fetzer (2014: 84) argues that the adverb *probably*, while appearing a few clauses before *I think*, does still affect its interpretation¹ (epistemic adverb underlined):

“You have something like fourteen hundred houses. With probably a couple of thousand more to come. You have a primary school. A health care centre. You have the whole of that land that can now be redeveloped. And **I think** you will find, in terms of jobs and in terms of investment, that the money is repaid”.

Simon-Vandenberg (2000), on the other hand, appears to take a wider approach to the co-text affecting the interpretation of *I think*, exploring in her study the effect of “[n]eighbouring clauses” (2000: 55) on the function of the epistemic phrase as well as noting how several expressions of modality in clauses near *I think* can create what she terms a “macro-modality” (2000: 56) that affects the interpretation of the phrase as a commitment-attenuator in conversations and a commitment-booster in political interviews. The following is an example of a commitment-attenuating “*I think*,” where such an interpretation is supported by the different expressions of low commitment by the speaker around the *I think* clause (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 56): “I don’t know, I can’t help looking at these things as a scientist, and **I think** it’s all rather hopeless, but you shouldn’t be influenced by me”.

Another difference between the two authors is in the actual elements within the co-text influencing the interpretation of *I think*, specifically, the discourse marker *well*. Simon-Vandenberg (2000: 55) proposes that the discourse marker *well* influences the interpretation of *I think* as commitment-attenuating, arguing that *well* is more prevalent in casual conversation than in political interviews. The author cites Aijmer (1997), who argues that *I think* is used mostly in informal conversations, as well as Jucker (1986), who argues that the occurrence of *well* in proximity to *I think* renders the latter a commitment-attenuating device. On the other hand, Fetzer (2014: 80) proposes that *well* influences the interpretation of *I think* as a commitment-booster, arguing that the discourse marker signals a continuation in the speaker’s argument with some potential contrast. Interestingly, Simon-Vandenberg (2000: 54) mentions that *so*, *therefore*, and *now* also function to connect the speaker’s argument to the previous one in the discourse, and so argues that *I think* preceded by such elements is of the commitment-boosting variety. This interpretation, however, is not extended to *well*, despite the fact that in both Simon-Vandenberg’s and Fetzer’s accounts, the discourse marker functions similarly. As such, on issues where the authors disagree, I will follow Fetzer’s account, taking her approach to be more methodologically sound and consistent.

4. Analysis

When analyzing the instances of *I think* in Corbyn’s interviews, they are predominantly of the commitment-boosting variety, providing support for the notion that it is partly through this use of epistemic modality that Corbyn constructs his identity as an authentic politician (Atkins and Turnbull, 2016; Stiers et al., 2019: 2). Indeed, starting with the Andrew Marr interview, held on November 17, 2019, every instance of *I think* uttered by Corbyn is of the commitment-

¹ However, the author also notes that, in the above example, the conjunction *and* is found right before the epistemic phrase, yielding what she refers to as a “salient discourse pattern” (Fetzer, 2014: 69), which seems to always produce a commitment-boosting *I think* despite the co-text in which the phrase appears.

boosting variety as analyzed per the criteria above. The following are some lines highlighting Corbyn's use of *I think* followed by an analysis of their commitment-boosting function.

Line (54) Jeremy Corbyn: Can I finish? Thank you. When we had the talks with the UK government over the summer we did have a very wide range of voices meeting the government on this, and **I think** it's very important that all parts of the country are represented in this and that's what I would seek to do.

(60) JC: They'll all be Labour voices that would have fought the election on the basis of the agreement we hope to reach with the European Union and which we'd put to the people of this country, 'cause **I do think** we've got to settle this and that we settle it by agreeing on a relationship with Europe either in or out.

(88) JC: Listen, we haven't had the election yet and we haven't had the negotiations yet. I want to make sure there's a credible offer of leave with these arrangements with the European Union or remain and the future relationship with Europe. And **I think** it's only right that if we fight the election on a manifesto that includes those options which is a way of bringing people together – which seems to me an adult approach to the whole thing.

(110) JC: **I think** you have to hold the referendum on the basis that those that wish to take part in it take part in it. **I think** what I would like to see in any future referendum is a very strict limit on spending on both sides, and also the ability to have – how shall I put it – check on the facts being offered by both sides in that referendum campaign. The problem with the last referendum campaign there wasn't any real examination of that.

(128) JC: No, **I don't think** so. But that would obviously be open for debate but **I do think** the important thing is to move forward on this so that we actually get to a position of making a decision.

(169) JC: Well, **I think** the movers of the motion had in mind the questions of family reunion of people from both the European Union and other parts of the world as well, because what you have is people that wholly legitimately make their homes and their contribution here, but have an artificial income level put on them if they're allowed to bring partners or children into this country and **I think** that is what is behind that motion.

Here, we can clearly see that every instance of Corbyn's use of the epistemic phrase *I think* is of the commitment-boosting variety. Indeed, in lines (54), (88), and (169), *I think* is preceded by the conjunction *and*, forming a salient discourse pattern marking a connection between the speaker's arguments such that the second argument is supporting the earlier one (Fetzer, 2014: 80). As such, *I think* in these lines is considered as commitment-boosting. In line (60), *I think* is preceded by an emphatic *do*, signaling its commitment-boosting function, while in line (110), both instances of *I think* appear clause initially, thus functioning as commitment-boosters. Additionally, the first instance appears near an expression of obligation, "you have to." In line (128), *I think* is preceded by the negator *no* and is itself negative in polarity, yielding a commitment-boosting function (Simon-Vandenberg, 2000: 52; Fetzer, 2014: 80). Finally, the first instance of *I think* in line (169) is also of the commitment-boosting variety, since it is preceded by the discourse marker *well*.

Similarly, in Corbyn's interview with Phillip Schofield and Holly Willoughby on "This Morning" on December 3, 2019, all of Corbyn's instances of *I think* are of the commitment-

boosting variety. Indeed, although Corbyn used the phrase only five times — which could be a function of the length of the interview; the Andrew Marr interview lasted for almost 29 minutes, while the interview with Schofield and Willoughby lasted a few seconds less than 13 minutes — each of these can be interpreted as boosting his commitment in the ideas, and ideals, that he expresses in his answers to the interviewers’ questions. The five instances are represented below, with the analysis following them.

Line (28) Jeremy Corbyn: **I think** prison sentences should be decided by courts and the management of the prison sentence should be also decided by a combination of the prison service. But the point I’m making very strongly is that our prison service is woefully underfunded and the rehabilitation and the programmes to stop people being radicalised have often been insufficient in prison, and **I think** the lesson from this horrible tragedy is that we have to improve that, and speaking to the friends of Jack who died in this.

(38) JC: I’m not calling for the abolition of any of our services. I am calling for accountability of our services, and that’s a point I’ve often made in Parliament. Indeed, I want to empower Parliament to hold government to account, because **I think** at the moment Parliament has insufficient powers to hold government to account.

(113) JC: Obviously. Obviously, I’m very sorry for everything that’s happened. But I want to make this clear. I am dealing with it. I have dealt with it. Other parties are also affected by antisemitism. Candidates have been withdrawn by the Liberal Democrats and the Conservatives and by us because of it. We just do not accept it in any form whatsoever. And **I think** the chief rabbi’s comments really ought to be taken for what they are. He hasn’t contacted me about it. I’m very happy to meet him, very happy to talk to him, very happy to talk to any representatives of any part of the Jewish community in our society because I recognise that antisemitism is a poison and it’s very dangerous.

(155) JC: Well, **I think** we’ll probably put one up about the 12th.

The general pattern of Corbyn using the epistemic phrase *I think* as a commitment-boosting device continues in this interview, too. Indeed, every instance of the phrase can be interpreted as boosting his commitment and, as such, presenting him as a politician who is confident of his ideas and ideals. In the turns beginning in lines (28) and (113), the phrase *I think* can be analyzed as boosting the speaker’s commitment: the phrase is clause initial in the turn starting at line (28) and it is preceded by the conjunction *and* in the turns starting at lines (28) and (113). In the turn starting at line (38), *I think* is preceded by the conjunction *because*, and in the turn starting at line (155), it is preceded by the discourse marker *well*; hence, both instances are of the commitment-boosting variety.

More evidence that part of Corbyn’s performance of authenticity is predicated on using the epistemic phrase *I think* comes from the Andrew Neil interview, held on November 26, 2019. This was, I believe, the most difficult and adversarial of the three pre-election interviews, partly because of Andrew Neil’s reputation as a tough interviewer (Bailey, 2021: 169) — in Power et al. (2020: 67), in fact, the authors refer to him as the “BBC Rottweiler” — and partly because of the interview’s focus on the issue of antisemitism in the Labour Party, which Wring et al. (2021: 130) argue has defined the media’s coverage of the party and its campaign during the 2019 general election.

Despite the ultra-adversarial nature of the interview with Andrew Neil, Corbyn still attempted to construct and project the authentic politician identity through the epistemic phrase *I think*, as he used it eight times during the 29-minute interview. The instances of *I think* and their analysis are presented below.

(10) JC: And as far as I'm concerned it's just not acceptable in any form in society. When the far-right are rising across Europe, using anti-Semitic tropes in order to intimidate people, then **I think** we've all got to stand up together on this.

(22) JC: But we've always, on a positive side, recognised the need for education, so we set up an education process in the party, education packs are available and also made it very clear that in government we would obviously support the Holocaust Education Trust and the need for all of our children to understand how the Holocaust came about and how the growth of the far-right in Germany led to that. And **I think** as a society we have to recognise that any form of racism is divisive and dangerous.

(121) JC: We will support the necessary funding to protect synagogues, protect temples, and protect mosques. We will protect the cemeteries also. We will not allow anti-Semitism in any form in our society because it is poisonous and divisive just as much as Islamophobia or far-right racism is. And **I think** we can agree on that.

(158) JC: Well, **I think** the country's become very divided over Brexit since 2016. That's clear. And we can't forever go on debating what happened in the referendum in 2016. People that voted remain and are living difficult lives, Universal Credit, private rented, poor lives —

(181) JC: Well, what I'm saying is that **I think** it's the role – it would be the role of the government to say this is the choice before you, the people of this country and we'd also make sure that there are spending rules and so on in that referendum.

(296) JC: **I think** they would also recognise that tax rates, in general, have gone down. That the levels of inequality have gone up. The levels of personal wealth for them have gone up enormously over the past ten years, and they can see all around them the crumbling of public services and the terrible levels of child poverty that exist across Britain.

(331) JC: – do attract an interest rate, but they also – it attracts a benefit, and **I think** you'll find that ultimately it becomes cost neutral.

(451) JC: Andrew, **I think** we also have to look at how we've created these dangers as well. That means the point I just raised. The point I just raised is a very serious one.

In these examples, similarly to the previous two interviews, we find that every instance of Corbyn's use of the epistemic phrase *I think* is of the commitment-boosting variety. Indeed, in the turns starting at lines (10), (22), (121), and (331), we find the phrase *I think* preceded by the conjunctions *that* (line 10) and *and* (lines 22, 121, 331), yielding a commitment-boosting function. In the turns starting at lines (158) and (181), the epistemic phrase is preceded by the discourse marker *well*, again signaling its function as boosting the speaker's commitment. In the turn starting at line (296), we find *I think* clause-initially, functioning as a commitment-booster, and in the turn starting at line (451), we find *I think* preceded only by a vocative element, *Andrew*, which is most likely used here because of the dialogic nature of the political interview (Berlin and Fetzer, 2012: 8; Craig, 2010: 76); the phrase also appears near a marker

of epistemic necessity, “we also **have to** look,” marking it as one of the commitment-boosting variety.

5. Discussion

What is clear from the above discussion is that Jeremy Corbyn consistently uses the epistemic phrase *I think* to project his commitment in the ideas, and ideals, he presents in response to the interviewers’ questions, which by nature relate to Corbyn’s, and Labour’s, position on the most pressing issues around which the 2019 general election was fought, namely: Brexit and a second remain/leave referendum (Curtice, 2020: 9) and how a Labour government would deal with the administrative, legal, and social changes brought about by a break from the European Union. In the Andrew Marr interview, for instance, the interviewer asked Corbyn about his plan to address the referendum results (lines 40 through 50 in the interview) and freedom of movement after a possible (at that time) exit from the EU (lines 150 to 160). It can be argued that Corbyn, in using the epistemic phrase *I think* in his replies to Andrew Marr, attempted to present himself as committing to addressing the results of the referendum in a way that incorporates as many voices as possible from different parts of the U.K. as well as the different parts of his party. Corbyn, then, attempted to present a more balanced — some say indecisive — approach to the results of the referendum rather than an outright support for remaining in the E.U. (Cutts et al., 2020: 5).

While the Andrew Marr interview generally focused on Brexit and a future Labour government’s outlook on it, the interview with Phillip Schofield and Holly Willoughby, as well as the one with Andrew Neil, focused more on allegations of antisemitism within the Labour party as well as the party’s, and Corbyn’s, outlook on issues of national security and the economy. There are, I believe, two intertwined strands of contextual factors here that motivate Corbyn’s use of *I think* to represent his commitment to his values and ideas: one is related to the allegations of antisemitism against the Labour party (Heppell, 2021: 648–649), and the other is related to the Labour Party’s core ideals of increasing public spending and reforming taxation laws (Gough, 2020: 15–16). Indeed, Corbyn’s use of *I think* in these two interviews could be construed as him committing to a stance against antisemitism and attempting to distance the party from such charges, as in the turn starting at line (113) in the Schofield and Willoughby interview and in the turns starting at lines (10), (22), and (121) in the Neil interview. Moreover, Corbyn’s use of *I think* in the turns starting at lines (28) and (38) in the Schofield and Willoughby interview and in the turns starting at lines (181), (296), and (331) in the Neil interview could be interpreted as him emphasizing his commitment to the Labour election manifesto, which included pledges related to increased public spending and taxation reforms — themselves traditional Labour issues that also appeared on the 2015 and 2017 election manifestos (Allen and Bara, 2021: 532–534).

The above section has presented an analysis of Corbyn’s use of the epistemic phrase *I think*, linking the interviewers’ questions as well as Corbyn’s response with the overall political context within the U.K. at the time. However, there is, it seems, an overall construction that cuts across the three interviews, that of Corbyn as *the* authentic politician. Indeed, whether he is discussing Brexit, antisemitism, or national tax reforms, Corbyn is presenting himself as someone whose inner values accord with what he’s saying (Umbach and Humphrey, 2017: 68; Iszatt-White et al., 2018: 535; Kissas, 2019: 5); that is, as an authentic politician. There appears to be a consensus that Corbyn’s image or persona of authenticity helped him win the 2015

Labour leadership contest (Iszatt-White et al., 2018: 1–2; Mueller et al., 2019: 2–4; Page, 2019: 1326) and helped Labour gain 30 seats in the 2017 U.K. general election (Whittle, 2020: 448–450; Morgan, 2021: 370–371). It could be argued, then, that Corbyn used this authentic identity to attempt to make the same gains in the 2019 general election, especially as he's faced with a divided electorate (Cooper and Cooper, 2020: 751), a divided Labour party (Cutts et al., 2020: 2; Prosser, 2020: 452), and possibly the most controversial issue affecting the U.K. in recent times (Curtice, 2020: 9; Fieldhouse et al., 2023: 1).

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to trace the construction of the authentic politician identity persona by Jeremy Corbyn. The starting point is the social constructionist conception of authenticity as an identity performed by individuals — a conceptualization that captures how authenticity is socially and interactionally constructed and relationally defined (Bucholtz, 2003: 407–408; Bucholtz and Hall, 2005; Goffee and Jones, 2005; Hernández-Campoy and Cutillas-Espinosa, 2010: 297–298). As such, we can view Corbyn's authenticity as an identity that is constructed and performed in different — usually mediated (Moffitt and Tormey, 2013: 388) — contexts involving some form of political discourse; that is, discourse “produced by and for political actors” (Wilson, 2015: 775). Particularly, the paper focuses on three sets of interviews with Corbyn held before the 2019 general election in the U.K., focusing mainly on Brexit, allegations of antisemitism within the Labour Party, and Corbyn's views on issues of national security and the economy.

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The second strand of research brought to bear in analyzing Corbyn's construction of authenticity is the (social constructionist) sociolinguistic approach to identities (Fina, 2010: 206, 214). Within this approach, identities are seen not as stable sets with fixed characteristics that involve, generally, socio-economic, geographical, and gender associations, but as constructions deployed and produced by speakers as a way of occupying a social space (Coupland, 2007b: 218; Charteris-Black, 2014: 537). These constructions are mutable, established and deployed in various contexts per the aims of the speaker (Eckert, 2012: 94). The key element within this conceptualization of identities is indexicality: a relationship between signs — whether verbal or non-verbal — and social meanings and values (Schilling, 2013: 340; Kiesling, 2013: 458). Through the concept of indexicality, sociolinguistic research on identity construction links specific discursive forms with social meanings, and it is these associations between sign and meaning that speakers rely on when constructing their identities. As such, indexicality allows us to explore how speakers construct their identities through their use of certain signs in specific contexts, and this is brought to bear in analyzing Corbyn's authentic politician identity in the three interviews mentioned above. In particular, the paper has focused on epistemic stance: how Corbyn expresses his commitment, or lack thereof, through the use of the epistemic phrase *I think*. The analysis of how Corbyn used *I think* shows that the ex-Labour leader uses the phrase exclusively, at least in the interviews explored in this paper, to show his commitment to the proposition and proposals that he expresses in response to the interviewers' questions and moves. It can be argued, as such, that Corbyn's authenticity is predicated, partially, on his use of *I think* to show his commitment to his ideas and ideals; to show that his own values, his inner self, as it were, accord with his propositions and proposals regarding the future of the U.K. as leader of the opposition and, possibly at the time, prime minister of the country.

One point that bears discussion here is the narrow scope of this analysis and the results thereof, and this is by design. For one thing, adopting a social-constructionist perspective on authenticity and identities, and the construction and performance of authenticity-as-an-identity, perforce involves accepting the notion that identities are malleable, mutable, deployed in different contexts for different aims by the speaker or, in this case, the politician. For another thing, adopting such a perspective centrally revolves around indexicality, positing a link between signs and social meanings that is not only context-dependent, but also recreated and imbued with new, possibly related, meanings each time a speaker uses a sign to establish his or her identity in a different context (Coupland, 2007b: 218–219; Eckert, 2008: 454). Combined, these two related factors mean that concretely defining an identity through the indexes that mark it is difficult because of the malleability of identities, and concretely linking indexes with identities is also difficult because of the mutable nature of indexes.

One way out of this paradox, I believe, is positing a narrow, contextually limited link between an index and the identity that it is used to mark or construct, such as the use of commitment-boosting epistemic phrases by Corbyn to construct the identity of the authentic politician. This approach neither presents too strong of an argument such that it generalizes across various domains without regard for context, nor does it present too weak of an argument such that the link between an identity and the discursive forms through which it is indexed is not evidenced. This approach, I believe, strikes a middle ground and presents useful results that can be built upon for future research on identities in political discourse, for despite the mutability of indexes, they are recognized as such because the social meanings they mark are part of the general values, ideas, and ideals embedded within a society, and despite the mutability of identities, they are recognized as such because they are constructed through indexes which link to these shared social meanings, valued, and ideals (Bucholtz and Hall, 2005: 594; Fina, 2010: 216; Schilling, 2013: 342).

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